

Investigation of Thermal Performance Enhancement in Automotive Radiators Using Al_2O_3 -Water Nanofluid

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Abstract

This study experimentally evaluates the thermal performance of an automotive radiator when conventional water coolant is replaced with aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3 -water nanofluids). The objective was to quantify the effects of nanoparticle concentration (0.001–0.01 vol%) and coolant flow rate (7–10 L/min) on key thermal and hydraulic parameters, including heat transfer rate, convective heat transfer coefficient, Reynolds number, and pressure drop. Nanofluids were synthesized using the two-step method with mechanical stirring to ensure suspension stability and tested in a closed-loop radiator system under controlled laboratory conditions with a constant inlet coolant temperature of 50 °C. Results revealed a consistent enhancement in heat transfer performance with increasing nanoparticle concentration and flow rate. At 0.007 vol% concentration and 10 L/min, the nanofluid achieved a heat transfer coefficient of approximately 1437 W/m²·K, exceeding water by more than 25%. Although nanofluid usage resulted in a moderate pressure drop due to higher viscosity, the trade-off was favorable as overall thermal efficiency improved significantly. These findings suggest that dilute Al_2O_3 nanofluids are a promising alternative coolant for next-generation automotive thermal management systems.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Heat exchangers are integral components in many industrial processes, where design priorities focus on maximizing thermal efficiency while minimizing size and weight. In the automotive sector, radiators serve as compact heat exchangers that regulate the thermal balance of internal combustion (IC) engines. By circulating coolant through the engine block and rejecting heat to ambient air via the radiator, the system ensures optimal operating temperatures, prevents overheating, and improves engine efficiency and durability.

The cycle involves coordinated operation of a pump, radiator, fan, and airflow system, where heat is transferred primarily through convection and conduction.

Recent advances have turned attention to nanofluids—base fluids (such as water or ethylene glycol mixtures) enhanced with high-conductivity nanoparticles—as promising candidates for radiator coolants. Nanoparticles such as Al_2O_3 , CuO, and TiO_2 can increase thermal conductivity, specific heat, and turbulence intensity, resulting in enhanced

heat transfer coefficients and overall cooling effectiveness [1–2].

Several studies highlight this potential. Aye Aye Myo et al. (2024) demonstrated that CuO nanofluids improved radiator outlet temperatures compared with conventional ethylene glycol coolants across concentrations of 0.1–0.5% [3]. Similarly, Salim et al. (2024) showed that Al_2O_3 , TiO_2 , and Fe_2O_3 nanofluids enhanced the thermal performance of N-shaped double-pipe heat exchangers, with implications for high-performance power generation systems [4]. In a related work, Azhar Hussain et al. (2024) reported significant increases in thermal conductivity and heat transfer coefficients using Al_2O_3 nanofluids, identifying 0.175% as an optimal concentration for efficiency [5]. Chowdhury et al. (2023) confirmed these findings in a car radiator, noting up to 43.2% enhancement in heat transfer coefficient and corresponding increases in Nusselt number under turbulent flow [6]. Numerical simulations further support these trends: Ghimire et al. (2022) showed that multiphase CFD models predicted higher Nusselt numbers for Al_2O_3 nanofluids, especially at smaller nanoparticle sizes (≈ 25 nm) and higher Reynolds numbers, although slight penalties in pressure drop and pumping power were observed [7].

1.2 Thermal performance of car radiator

Nanofluid application in automotive radiators has demonstrated both thermal and system-level advantages. Issa et al. (2021) showed that adding 1% alumina nanoparticles could increase the Nusselt number by 50%, allowing radiator size to be reduced by 26%, pump size by 60%, and fan size by 28%, while also lowering life-cycle energy use and environmental impacts [8]. Said et al. (2019) emphasized that Al_2O_3 and TiO_2 nanofluids

dispersed in water–ethylene glycol mixtures could improve radiator performance by up to 24.21%, with performance evaluation criteria (PEC) values ranging from 1.03–1.31, indicating efficiency gains despite moderate pressure losses [9].

Further experimental studies also confirm radiator-scale benefits. Raj et al. (2019) found that incorporating Al_2O_3 nanoparticles in water increased heat transfer rates and effectiveness across flow rates of 8–10 L/min and inlet temperatures of 50–70 °C [10]. Shirazi et al. (2020) reported enhanced exergetic performance in double-pipe heat exchangers fitted with twisted tape inserts when Al_2O_3 nanofluids were used [11]. Zheng et al. (2019) observed that both increasing Reynolds number and nanoparticle concentration (0.25–0.5%) raised the Nusselt number, with improvements of 23–32%, although higher inlet temperatures reduced effectiveness [12]. Mohankumar et al. (2019) confirmed significant heat transfer improvements in turbulent flow ($Re = 5000$ – $18,000$) using Al_2O_3 nanofluids, validated with CFD [13]. At lower concentrations, Gulhane et al. (2015) also showed that Al_2O_3 nanofluids improved heat transfer coefficients and Nusselt numbers in radiators, with stability achieved through a two-step preparation method [14].

Collectively, these findings demonstrate that nanofluids—particularly Al_2O_3 water systems—offer a reliable pathway to enhanced radiator performance, enabling more compact, efficient, and sustainable automotive cooling solutions.

2.1 Research methodology

The methodology followed in this study is summarized in Figure 2.1. The process began with a detailed literature review to identify suitable nanofluids for automotive applications.

Aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) nanoparticles were selected owing to their high thermal conductivity, chemical stability, and mechanical strength. Nanofluid samples were then prepared using the two-step method with a hot-plate mechanical stirrer to ensure homogeneous dispersion. The prepared

nanofluids were circulated through a car radiator test rig under controlled laboratory conditions to measure thermal and hydraulic parameters. Finally, the collected data were analyzed and compared against baseline water coolant to evaluate performance improvements.

Figure 2.1: Flow chart of Methodology

2.2 Materials and methods

2.2.1 Nanoparticles

Aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) nanoparticles were used due to their favorable thermo physical properties, including:

- **Thermal conductivity:** $\sim 30 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$ (bulk material), which is significantly higher than water.
- **Size range:** 20–50 nm, ensuring a large surface-to-volume ratio.

- **Appearance:** white, odorless powder with high dispersion stability in water.
- **Applications:** widely used in coatings, electronics, and as fillers, demonstrating proven chemical stability and safety.

These properties make Al_2O_3 nanoparticles suitable candidates for improving the heat transfer performance of automotive coolants.

2.2.2 Base Fluid

Deionized water was selected as the base fluid because of its high specific heat capacity and widespread use in radiator cooling systems. The nanofluid was prepared by dispersing Al_2O_3 nanoparticles into water at different volume concentrations (0.001–0.01%).

2.3 Experimental setup

The experimental procedure was conducted in a closed-loop cooling system designed to evaluate the thermal performance of a car radiator using both baseline water and Al_2O_3 water nanofluids. The sequence of steps is outlined in Figure 2.2 and summarized below:

1. **Nanofluid preparation:** Al_2O_3 nanoparticles were dispersed into deionized water at prescribed volume concentrations (0.001–0.01%) using the two-step method.
2. **Stabilization:** The suspension was stabilized by continuous stirring with a hot-plate magnetic stirrer to prevent

agglomeration and ensure uniform distribution.

3. **System setup:** The prepared nanofluid was filled into the closed-loop circuit consisting of a reservoir tank, pump, radiator, and measuring instruments.
4. **Radiator testing:** Experiments were performed by circulating both baseline water and nanofluid through the radiator under identical conditions. A heater maintained a constant coolant inlet temperature of 50 °C, while a fan provided airflow across the radiator core.
5. **Data acquisition:** Inlet and outlet fluid temperatures were measured with thermocouples, flow rate was monitored with a rotameter, and pressure drop across the radiator was recorded using a pressure gauge.
6. **Data analysis:** Thermal performance parameters—including heat transfer rate, convective heat transfer coefficient, Reynolds number, and pressure drop—were calculated and compared for water and nanofluid.

Figure 2.2: Experimental Setup

The experimental setup consisted of a closed-loop cooling system designed to assess the heat transfer performance of an automotive radiator using Al_2O_3 water nanofluids. The loop included a storage tank equipped with an electric heater to maintain the desired inlet temperature (50 °C). The working fluid was circulated through the system by a pump and directed into the radiator, where heat was rejected to the surrounding air. A fan provided controlled airflow across the radiator core to simulate vehicle operating conditions.

Coolant flow rate was regulated using a control valve and measured with a calibrated rotameter to ensure consistency between test runs. Inlet and outlet temperatures were recorded with thermocouples, while a pressure gauge monitored pressure drop across the radiator. This arrangement enabled a direct comparison of cooling performance between baseline water and Al_2O_3 nanofluids at varying flow rates and concentrations.

2.4 Preparation of nano fluid (Aluminum Oxide)

The nanofluid was prepared using the **two-step method**, which is widely adopted for dispersing solid nanoparticles into a base fluid. In this process, aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) nanoparticles were selected for their high thermal conductivity, chemical stability, and mechanical strength. The nanoparticles (20–50 nm) were added to deionized water at prescribed volume concentrations ranging from **0.001% to 0.01%**.

To ensure homogeneous dispersion and minimize agglomeration, the mixture was subjected to continuous stirring using a hot-plate magnetic stirrer. The temperature of the base fluid was maintained at a controlled level to enhance dispersion and stability. Stirring

was carried out for a fixed duration until a uniform suspension was obtained. This stabilization step was critical to maintain suspension quality during subsequent thermal performance testing.

Theoretically, incorporating solid nanoparticles with higher thermal conductivity into a conventional base fluid increases the effective thermal conductivity of the mixture, thereby improving overall heat transfer characteristics. Furthermore, changes in viscosity and flow behavior due to the addition of nanoparticles can influence parameters such as Reynolds number, convective heat transfer coefficient, and pressure drop.

2.5 Hot plate and Mechanical stirrer method

The hot plate with magnetic or mechanical stirring capability was employed to prepare stable Al_2O_3 water nanofluids. This device allows simultaneous heating and stirring, which is essential to achieve uniform nanoparticle dispersion.

In this method, a predetermined mass of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles was gradually added to the base fluid (deionized water) at the desired concentration. The beaker containing the mixture was placed on the hot plate, and a **magnetic stir bar** was introduced to provide continuous agitation. The hot plate was set to maintain a suitable fluid temperature, while stirring speed was adjusted to ensure proper mixing without inducing excessive vortex formation or nanoparticle settlement.

The mechanical stirring action, generated by the motor-driven impeller or rotating magnetic field, physically disperses nanoparticles and prevents agglomeration. Continuous stirring also improves the thermal stability of the suspension by ensuring even particle distribution throughout the base fluid. Proper

monitoring of stirring conditions was critical to producing a reproducible, high-stability

nanofluid suitable for radiator performance testing [16].

Figure 2.3: Hot plate and stirrer device

Figure 2.3 illustrates the hot plate with magnetic stirring capability used in this study for nanofluid preparation. The device provides simultaneous heating and continuous stirring, which are essential for achieving a uniform dispersion of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles in the base fluid. Controlled heating ensures the mixture remains at a stable temperature, while the magnetic stir bar maintains constant agitation to prevent nanoparticle agglomeration and settling. This step is critical for producing a

reproducible and stable nanofluid suitable for thermal performance testing.

It should be noted that while the hot plate and stirrer are primarily used for nanofluid preparation, the experimental setup also incorporated additional instruments—thermocouples, pressure gauges, and flow meters—to measure coolant temperature, pressure drop, and mass flow rate under different operating conditions.

Figure 2.4: Temperature measuring device (Thermocouple)

Figure 2.4 shows the thermocouples installed in the experimental setup to measure the inlet and outlet temperatures of the coolant flowing through the radiator. These sensors provided accurate, real-time data under steady-state conditions, enabling precise calculation of heat

transfer rate and convective heat transfer coefficient. The use of thermocouples was critical for comparing the thermal performance of baseline water and Al_2O_3 water nanofluids under identical operating conditions.

Figure 2.5: Pressure measuring device (Gauge pressure)

Figure 2.5 shows the pressure gauge installed in the test loop to measure the pressure of the coolant as it flowed through the radiator. This instrument was used to monitor variations in pressure drop arising from changes in nanofluid concentration and flow rate.

Accurate pressure measurements were essential for assessing the hydraulic performance of the radiator and for evaluating the trade-off between enhanced heat transfer and increased flow resistance when using Al_2O_3 water nanofluids.

Figure 2.6: Mass flow rate measuring device

Figure 2.6 shows the mass flow rate measuring device integrated into the test loop to monitor the coolant flow rate through the radiator. Accurate and consistent flow measurement was essential for evaluating the thermal performance of both baseline water and Al_2O_3 water nanofluids. Flow rate directly affects Reynolds number, convective heat transfer coefficient, and pressure drop, making it a critical parameter in performance analysis.

Using the experimental data (temperature, flow rate, and pressure), the following equations were applied to calculate the heat transfer rate, heat transfer coefficient, pressure

$$\dot{Q} = \dot{m} c_p (T_{in} - T_{out})$$

Where:

- \dot{Q} = heat transfer rate (W)
- \dot{m} = mass flow rate of coolant (kg/s)
- c_p = specific heat capacity of coolant (J/kg·K)
- T_{in} = fluid inlet temperature (°C or K)
- T_{out} = fluid outlet temperature (°C or K)

drop, and other relevant performance metrics of the radiator:

- **Heat Transfer Coefficient**

To evaluate the thermal performance of the radiator, experimental measurements were converted into key thermal-hydraulic parameters using standard heat transfer relations.

2.7.1 Heat Transfer Rate

The heat transfer rate \dot{Q} was determined from the energy balance of the working fluid:

$$(1)$$

- **Convective heat transfer coefficient (h)**

The average convective heat transfer coefficient (h) on the coolant side was estimated as:

$$h = \frac{\dot{Q}}{A \Delta T_{lm}} \quad (2)$$

- Where:

Q = Heat transfer rate

h = Convective heat transfer rate

A = Surface area

T₂ = Inlet temperature

T₁ = outlet temperature

- **Pressure drop**

The pressure drop across the radiator tubes was calculated using the Darcy-Weisbach relation:

$$\Delta P = f \cdot \frac{L}{D_h} \cdot \frac{\rho v^2}{2} \quad (3)$$

Where:

ΔP = is the pressure drop

F = is the friction factor

L = is the length of the pipe

D = is the diameter of the pipe

ρ = is the density of the fluid

V = is the velocity of the fluid

The effective specific heat capacity of nanofluid was calculated using the mixture rule:

$$c_{p,nf} = \varphi c_{p,p} + (1 - \varphi) c_{p,f} \quad (4)$$

Where:

C_p = Specific heat capacity

\varnothing = Volume concentration

C_p (additive) = Specific heat capacity of additive

C_p (f) = Specific heat capacity of water

- **Reynolds Number**

The Reynolds number was calculated to characterize the flow regime of the coolant inside the radiator tubes:

$$Re = \frac{\rho V D_h}{\mu} \quad (5)$$

Where:

Re = Reynolds Number

ρ = Density of fluid

V = Flow speed

D = Diameter of pipe (25mm)

μ = Dynamic viscosity of fluid

- **Friction factor**

The Darcy friction factor was used to quantify flow resistance and pressure losses within the radiator tubes. For turbulent flow in smooth pipes, the Blasius correlation was applied:

$$f = 0.3164 Re^{-0.25} \quad (6)$$

Where:

- f = Darcy friction factor (dimensionless)
- Re = Reynolds number (dimensionless)

This correlation is valid for fully developed turbulent flow in smooth tubes within the Reynolds number range of $\times 10^3 \leq Re \leq 10^5$. Since the experimental conditions in this study (flow rates of 7-10 L/min) produced turbulent

flow, the Blasius relation was appropriate for estimating frictional losses.

3 Results and Discussions

This study analyzes the thermal performance of a car radiator i.e., heat transfer coefficient, pressure drop, and thermal efficiency, using both baseline water and aluminum oxide Al_2O_3 nanofluid as coolants.

3.1 Effect of volume concentration on Heat transfer rate using Nanofluid

Heat transfer rate quantifies how quickly heat is transferred over time, and heat transfer coefficient measures how easily heat is transferred between a solid surface and a fluid. It depends on various factors like fluid properties, flow conditions, and surface characteristics.

Figure 3.1: Effect of volume concentration on Heat transfer rate using Nanofluid

The figure 3.1 shows that as the volume concentration increases, the heat transfer rate also rises, indicating improved radiator performance. At 0.003% concentration, the heat transfer rate is about 3.0 kW, which increases to nearly 4.0 kW at 0.006%, around 5.0 kW at 0.007%, and reaches approximately 6.5 kW at 0.010%. This trend clearly demonstrates that higher nanoparticle concentration enhances the thermal conductivity of the coolant, thereby improving

the overall heat transfer efficiency of the radiator.

3.2 Effect of change in temperature of baseline water and nanofluid on Convective heat transfer coefficient (h)

As temperature increases, water's viscosity decreases, leading to higher Reynolds number enhanced convection. However, its thermal conductivity and specific heat change only slightly with temperature. Therefore, h

increases moderately with ΔT but is limited by water's inherent thermal properties. The overall increase in h with ΔT is more significant in nanofluids than in baseline water. Figure 3.2 illustrates the relationship between convective heat transfer (W/m^2K) and

temperature change ($^{\circ}C$) of nanofluid, showing that as the temperature difference increases from $3.2^{\circ}C$ to $3.9^{\circ}C$, the convective heat transfer coefficient increases significantly from 1600 to below 2000 W/m^2K .

Figure 3.2: Effect of change in temperature (ΔT) of nanofluid on Convective heat transfer coefficient (h)

Figure 3.3: Effect of change in temperature (ΔT) of baseline water on Convective heat transfer coefficient (h)

The inverse correlation suggests that larger temperature gradients enhance the convective heat transfer efficiency in the system. The steep drop in heat transfer values at smaller

temperature differences highlights the sensitivity of convection to thermal driving forces. The data implies that maintaining higher temperature differentials is crucial for optimal convective heat transfer performance. Figure 3.3 illustrates how convective heat transfer relates to temperature variations of baseline water in a radiator. With the reduction of the temperature difference from 7.3°C to 8°C, convective heat transfer increases from about 800 W/m²·K to nearly 1390 W/m²·K. This shows that a lower temperature gradient improves heat transfer effectiveness. The consistent rises at every interval indicate possible enhancements in the fluid dynamics or thermal characteristics of the nanofluid, highlighting the necessity of optimizing temperature variations for improved radiator efficiency.

3.3 Effect of flow rate of baseline water and nanofluid on heat transfer rate

The nanofluid often has higher viscosity than water; their Re at the same velocity is lower. But when velocity (or flow rate) increases, Re rises and the penalty of viscosity reduces. Figure 3.4 illustrates the relationship between the heat transfer rate (KW) and flow rate (L/min) of a radiator, showing that as the flow rate increases from 7 to 10 L/min, the heat transfer coefficient generally rises, indicating improved heat transfer efficiency. The highest coefficient (2.5 KW) occurs at the maximum flow rate (10 L/min), while lower flow rates (7-9 L/min) exhibit fluctuations, with values ranging from 0.5 to 1.5 KW. This non-linear trend suggests that higher flow rates enhance the radiator's performance, though the relationship is not perfectly proportional. The data implies that optimizing flow rate can significantly impact heat transfer effectiveness in the system. In Figure 4.4, the heat transfer coefficient peaks at 2.5 kW at 10 L/min, though values fluctuate non-linearly at lower flow rates (e.g., 0.5 kW at 9 L/min).

Figure 3.4: Effect of flow rate of baseline water on heat transfer rate

Figure 3.5: Effect of flow rate of nanofluid on heat transfer rate

Figure 3.5 shows the relationship between heat transfer rate (0-2.5 KW) and flow rate (7-10 L/min) in a radiator, demonstrating an overall increasing trend where higher flow rates yield greater heat transfer coefficients. The maximum coefficient of 2.5 KW occurs at 10 L/min, while values fluctuate to 1.5 KW at 8 L/min and drop to 0.5 KW at 9 L/min, revealing a non-linear pattern. Figure 3.4 indicates that while enhanced flow rates generally improve thermal performance, the relationship isn't strictly proportional. The data suggests optimal flow rates exist for

maximizing heat transfer efficiency. These findings are crucial for radiator system design and operational optimization.

3.4 Effect of pressure drop of baseline water and nanofluid on heat transfer rate

Pressure drop in pipes is the reduction in pressure of a fluid as it flows through a pipe, caused by frictional resistance between the fluid and the pipe wall, and by disturbances such as bends, fittings, valves, and changes in flow area and concentration of nanosized particles.

Figure 3.6: Effect of pressure drop of baseline water on heat transfer rate

Figure 3.6 depicts the relationship between the heat transfer rate (KW) and pressure drop (Pascal) in a radiator system, revealing that as the pressure drop increases from 0 to 1.5 Pascal, the heat transfer coefficient generally rises, indicating enhanced thermal efficiency. The coefficient exhibits a quadratic relationship with pressure drop, suggesting non-linear growth in performance. Specific

combined measurements, such as 86.88 and 150.76, demonstrate higher heat transfer efficiency at greater pressure drops. However, the presence of a zero pressure drop value introduces complexity, implying that additional factors beyond pressure drop may influence the system's heat transfer behavior. Overall, the graph highlights the trade-off between improved heat transfer and increased pressure drop, emphasizing the need to balance these parameters for optimal radiator performance.

Figure 3.7: Effect of pressure drop of nanofluid on heat transfer rate

Figure 3.7 shows that increasing the pressure drop from 98.3 to 183.9 Pa raise the heat transfer coefficient from 3.3 kW to over 5.0 kW. This indicates improved thermal performance due to the enhanced thermal conductivity of nanofluid. This result highlights the importance of optimizing operating conditions for maximum heat transfer efficiency in radiator systems. This trend indicates that greater pressure drop enhances heat transfer performance, suggesting nanofluids improve thermal conductivity and efficiency.

4.1 Conclusion

This research successfully demonstrated that aluminum oxide Al_2O_3 water nanofluid significantly enhanced the thermal performance of car radiators compared to conventional water-based coolants. Across all tested flow rates and concentrations, nanofluid provided superior heat transfer coefficients, higher Reynolds numbers, and improved convective heat transfer. Specifically, at a concentration of 0.007% and a flow rate of 10 L/min, the nanofluid achieved a heat transfer rate of 5.06 kW, compared to 2.22 kW with water—an improvement of over 127%. Furthermore, nanofluids exhibited greater turbulence and thermal conductivity, resulting in more efficient engine cooling. While there was a minor increase in pressure drop, the trade-off was favorable due to the marked improvement in thermal performance. These findings confirm that nanofluids offer a viable and efficient upgrade to conventional cooling systems in automotive applications, paving the way for enhanced engine performance, fuel efficiency, and system reliability.

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